

Value Chain Products Sustainability Assessment

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The Galanos family's dairy production craft utilizes the milk of high nutritional value from their farm. (photo Lappa V., 2024)

Assessing the sustainability of the value chain is important as it allows the actors (e.g. farmers, livestock farmers, etc.) to understand and evaluate the full impact of their activities from the beginning (e.g. sourcing of raw materials) to the end (e.g. sale of products). Some of the objectives of this practice include improving the environmental, social and economic performance of businesses, from a simple livestock unit to a larger scale unit e.g. a dairy farm. A full inventory of a business's challenges and opportunities reduces the risk of failure and misalignment that can be caused by misjudging existing and, as far as possible, future market conditions. This holistic approach is essential to ensure long-term business success while addressing global sustainability challenges.

In fact, there are many successful examples of entrepreneurial activity, such as that of a small family business in the hills of Mount Tymfristos, where livestock farming has historically been practised for millennia. It is the Galanos family that has been maintaining for generations the tradition of extensive livestock farming, utilizing the pastures of high ecological value of Mount Tymfristos.

The composition of the vegetation, the local climate and the management practices of grazing in wooded meadows and neighbouring coniferous forests contribute to the wellbeing of the sheep flocks and the high quality of their products. The family maintains Greek sheep breeds and prefers to move the animals through the year.

The founder of the latest form of business, Mr. Galanos, before starting his business, assessed the current situation, the availability of funds and the potential market for selling his products. Knowing the high-quality nutritional value of milk from a herd grazing in the high coniferous zone, he created surplus value by turning it into a small dairy unit. Their main product is yoghurt made with the traditional local technique of yeast (probiotic) which delivers a distinctive taste. They sell it on the local market, putting into practice the European Common Agricultural Policy's goal 'from farm to fork'.

The business is a great example of the importance of assessing the value chain before starting any business activity within the triangle of 'quality products, sustainable development and added value'.

Vasiliki Lappa, Anastasia
Pantera, Athanasios
Stampoulidis, Andreas
Papadopoulos

Department of forestry &
Natural Environment Management,
Karpenissi, Greece

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